

Complexes of derivatives of 4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole as potential pesticides

Nisha Singh, Naresh K. Sangwan* and Kuldip S. Dhindsa

Department of Chemistry, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004, India

Manuscript received 22 March 2000, revised 4 September 2000, accepted 30 November 2000

Cyclization of 3-aryl-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-ones with hydrazine hydrate in refluxing acetic acid furnishes 1-acetyl-5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1*H*-pyrazoles (HL¹-HL⁴, Ar = Ph, 4-CH₃O-C₆H₄, 2-furyl, 2-thienyl, respectively). Refluxing of ligands HL¹-HL⁴ with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions (M) in basic medium affords complexes of the type [ML₂]. The ligands behave as tridentate, coordinating through oxygen of the 1-acetyl group, the phenolic oxygen after deprotonation and N-2 of the pyrazole ring. The ligands HL¹, HL², HL⁴ and their complexes show promising antifungal activity.

The synthesis and biological activities of complexes of hydrazones and acid hydrazides have been studied extensively¹. These complexing moieties are incorporated in a cyclic framework in 1-acyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles making the latter suitable for complexation^{2,3}. Moreover, such pyrazoles are also well known for their various biological activities⁴. In our recent studies^{3,5}, we observed marked influence of coordination of 4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles with transition metal ions on their antifungal activity. We report herein the synthesis of complexes of 1-acetyl-5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1*H*-pyrazoles with transition metal ions and their *in vitro* mycelial growth-inhibitory activity against some economically important phytopathogenic fungal pests.

Results and Discussion

The ligands, 1-acetyl-5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1*H*-pyrazoles (HL¹-HL⁴) were prepared by refluxing 3-aryl-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-ones (1-4) with hydrazine hydrate in glacial acetic acid (Scheme 1). The ligands displayed characteristic IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

The two magnetically non-equivalent protons at C₄ in HL¹-HL⁴, due to an adjacent chiral center at C₅, appeared at different chemical shifts in ¹H NMR spectra. The coupling constants of such protons are known⁶ to be influenced by the nature of substituents at N-1 and are, therefore, not reliable for their assignments. However, the assignments of protons at C₄ were made on the basis of their characteristic chemical shifts⁷. The C₄-H resonating upfield (δ 3.30–3.58) was assigned *trans* to C₅-H and that resonating downfield (δ 3.70–3.86) was assigned *cis* to C₅-H. The coupling constant *J*_{4,5-*trans*} was found to be smaller (4–5 Hz) in comparison with *J*_{4,5-*cis*} (11–12 Hz) in agreement with those described earlier⁷. The C₅-H appeared at δ 5.52–5.83. The structures were further supported by elemental analysis data.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of ligands HL¹-HL⁴.

The complexes (Table 1) are stable under atmospheric conditions and insoluble in most of the common organic solvents except polar solvents such as DMSO and nitrobenzene. The low molar conductance indicated the non-electrolytic nature of all the complexes. Elemental analyses and molecular weight data indicated 1 : 2 metal : ligand stoichiometry with the general formula [ML₂], where L is the appropriate deprotonated ligand HL¹-HL⁴ and M is Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}.

IR spectra : All the ligands displayed characteristic IR bands at 3100–3010 (OH H-bonded), 1660–1630 (C=O), 1590–1580 (C=N), 1240–1230 (C–O) and 850–810 cm⁻¹ (N–N)⁸. The characteristic furanyl and thienyl ring vibrations of HL³ and HL⁴ were observed at 590 and 565 cm⁻¹, respectively. In the spectra of all the complexes, the 3100–3050 cm⁻¹ band was absent and the ν_{C–O} band suffered positive shift (17–52 cm⁻¹) indicating coordination of phenolic OH via oxygen after deprotonation. Further the complexes showed a negative shift (10–32 cm⁻¹) for ν_{C=N} and a positive shift (10–35 cm⁻¹) for ν_{N–N}, indicating coordination of the ligands via N-2 of the pyrazole ring⁹. A negative shift (15–35 cm⁻¹) for the carbonyl group undoubtedly indicated the participation of this group in coordination¹⁰. The furan and thiophene ring stretching vibrations remained

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Complex	Melting/Decomp. (D) point (°C)	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
[Mn(L ¹) ₂]	>220	9.4 (9.0)	5.75
[Mn(L ²) ₂]	>220	8.1 (8.2)	6.00
[Mn(L ³) ₂]	>220	9.7 (9.3)	5.81
[Mn(L ⁴) ₂]	>220	8.5 (8.8)	5.96
[Co(L ¹) ₂]	>220	9.1 (9.5)	4.95
[Co(L ²) ₂]	>220	8.4 (8.7)	4.70
[Co(L ³) ₂]	>220	10.2 (9.9)	5.00
[Co(L ⁴) ₂]	>220	9.2 (9.4)	4.80
[Ni(L ¹) ₂]	140 (D)	9.9 (9.5)	2.98
[Ni(L ²) ₂]	>220	9.1 (8.7)	2.98
[Ni(L ³) ₂]	>220	10.1 (9.8)	3.08
[Ni(L ⁴) ₂]	>220	9.5 (9.3)	3.10
[Cu(L ¹) ₂]	137	10.4 (10.2)	2.10
[Cu(L ²) ₂]	>220	8.9 (9.3)	2.15
[Cu(L ³) ₂]	220	11.0 (10.6)	1.97
[Cu(L ⁴) ₂]	190 (D)	9.7 (10.0)	1.95
[Zn(L ¹) ₂]	142 (D)	10.9 (10.5)	–
[Zn(L ²) ₂]	>220	10.0 (9.6)	–
[Zn(L ³) ₂]	>220	11.1 (10.8)	–
[Zn(L ⁴) ₂]	>220	10.2 (10.3)	–

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

unaltered in the spectra of the complexes of the ligands HL³ and HL⁴, respectively, suggesting non-participation of their oxygen and sulfur in the coordination. The participation of N-2, the phenolic oxygen after deprotonation and the carbonyl group, was also supported by the appearance of new bands in the far-IR region at 500–418 (M–O) and 440–400 cm⁻¹ (M–N)¹¹.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra : The effective magnetic moment values of the complexes calculated from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities are presented in Table 1. The effective magnetic moments of the Mn^{II} complexes (5.75–6.00 B.M.) are characteristic of high-spin Mn^{II} complexes. The electronic spectra of the complexes showed weak absorption bands in the regions 18490–19220, 21432–22163, 24656–25386 and 28037–28765 cm⁻¹ assigned to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g(G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(D) transitions, respectively, suggesting a distorted octahedral geometry for the Mn^{II} complexes¹².

The Co^{II} complexes displayed magnetic moments in the range of 4.70–5.00 B.M. indicating the presence of three unpaired electrons with significant orbital contribution and a high spin octahedral stereochemistry¹². Three bands observed at 8000–8660, 17040–17770 and 21000–21730 cm⁻¹ were assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F) →

⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions, respectively. The appearance of these bands together with energy ratio ν₂/ν₁ of the complexes (2.04–2.10)¹³, nephelauxetic ratio (0.923–0.941), 10Dq (9038–9040 cm⁻¹) and LFSE (86.49–86.51 kJ mol⁻¹) suggested an octahedral configuration around Co^{II}. The low value of Racah interelectronic repulsion parameter B (880–914 cm⁻¹) than the free-ion value (971 cm⁻¹), suggested a weak covalent character of the metal-ligand bond¹⁴.

The effective magnetic moment values (2.98–3.10 B.M.) of the Ni^{II} complexes and the appearance of three bands in the regions 10020–10200 [³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁)], 15580–15775 [³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂)] and 24405–24590 [³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃)] cm⁻¹ in their electronic spectra suggested their octahedral geometry. Their ligand field parameters 10Dq, B, β and LFSE were in the range 10020–10200 cm⁻¹, 651–662 cm⁻¹, 0.625–0.636 and 143.83–146.41 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. The energy ratio ν₂/ν₁ for the complexes was 1.55 as required for octahedral complexes¹⁵. The B value (651–662 cm⁻¹) was less than the free-ion value because of decreased interelectronic repulsion resulting from electron delocalization¹⁶.

The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complexes (1.95–2.15 B.M.) corresponded to a single unpaired electron with significant orbital contribution. The increase from the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) might be due to Jahn-Teller distortion¹⁷. A broad band at 15400–15700 cm⁻¹ due to the ²E_g → ²T_{2g} transition in the electronic spectra suggested distorted octahedral configuration for the complexes. Further, absence of band below 10000 cm⁻¹ excluded the possibility of a tetrahedral structure¹⁸. The observed values of 10Dq (15400–15700 cm⁻¹) and LFSE (110.52–112.67 kJ mol⁻¹) also supported the proposed geometry.

The Zn^{II} complexes were diamagnetic. However, on the basis of their elemental analyses, infrared spectra, molecular weight and molar conductance studies, octahedral structures were proposed for the Zn^{II} complexes.

Fungicidal activity : The *in vitro* mycelial growth-inhibitory activity of the ligands and their complexes was evaluated against four phytopathogenic fungi, namely, *Alternaria alternata* (Fr.) Keissler from radish siliqua, *Colletotrichum falcatum* Went. from sugar cane, *Fusarium oxysporum* Schlecht. emend Snyd and Hans f sp ciceri (Padwick) Snyd and Hans from chick pea and *Rhizoctonia bataticola* (Taub.) Butl. from green gram. The fungi were maintained on Czapek's Dox Agar Slants at 5°. The growth-inhibitory activity was tested in broths at 28 ± 1° using the two-fold serial dilution technique² by dissolving the compounds in DMSO. Bavistin [2-(methoxycarbonyl)benzi-

midazole] was used as a standard for comparing the activity of the test compounds.

In general, ligands HL¹, HL² and HL⁴ and their complexes showed promising activity against *A. alternata* and *C. falcatum*. *F. oxysporum* and *R. bataticola* showed least sensitivity against all the ligands and their complexes studied. The most active ligand against *A. alternata* and *C. falcatum* was found to be HL⁴ (MIC 12.5 and 50 µg ml⁻¹, respectively) followed by HL² (MIC 25 and 50 µg ml⁻¹, respectively). The growth of both these fungi was also inhibited at 50 and 100 µg ml⁻¹ concentration respectively by ligands HL¹ and HL³. Ligands HL¹ and HL² showed activity against *F. oxysporum* at 100 µg ml⁻¹ while HL³ and HL⁴ were ineffective upto a concentration of 100 µg ml⁻¹ against this fungus. The growth of *R. bataticola* was inhibited by HL² and HL³ at 50 and 25 µg ml⁻¹, respectively, whereas, HL¹ and HL⁴ were unable to prevent its growth upto 100 µg ml⁻¹. Although, the activity in general remained unaltered on complexation, however, the activity of HL¹ was improved significantly (MIC 6.25, 12.5 and 3.13 µg ml⁻¹ against *A. alternata*, *C. falcatum* and *R. bataticola*, respectively) on complexation with Mn^{II}. Other noteworthy improvement in activity were observed for Ni^{II} complex of HL¹ against *F. oxysporum* (MIC 50 µg ml⁻¹), Cu^{II} complex of HL³ against *A. alternata* and *C. falcatum* (MIC 50 µg ml⁻¹ against both) and Mn^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of HL⁴ against *R. bataticola* (MIC 50 µg ml⁻¹ for both). In comparison, the standard fungicide, bavistin inhibited the growth of *A. alternata*, *C. falcatum*, *F. oxysporum* and *R. bataticola* at concentrations 0.79, 1.56, 3.13 and 0.79 µg ml⁻¹, respectively. Though the ligands and their complexes studied showed less activity than that of the standard fungicide, yet the promising activity shown by some of the compounds offers a lead to develop useful pesticides by further chemical manipulation.

Experimental

1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (1), 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (2), 3-furyl-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (3) and 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(thienyl)prop-2-en-1-one (4) were available from our earlier studies⁵. All other chemicals were procured from commercial suppliers. The solvents were distilled prior to use.

Synthesis of ligands : Ligands HL¹-HL⁴ were synthesized by refluxing a mixture of the appropriate propenone (1-4; 0.1 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (2 ml, excess) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) for 10 h. The mixture was then cooled

and poured in ice-water with stirring. The precipitated solid was washed with water, dried and crystallized from methanol (yields 80–91%) : HL¹, m.p. 126°, δ 2.39 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.30 (1H, dd, *J* 5 and 18 Hz, *trans* C₄-H), 3.86 (1H, dd, *J* 12 and 18 Hz, *cis* C₄-H), 5.57 (1H, dd, *J* 5 and 12 Hz, C₅-H), 6.91–7.39 (9H, m, ArH), 10.28 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable); HL², 142°, δ 2.37 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.30 (1H, dd, *J* 5 and 18 Hz, *trans* C₄-H), 3.78 (3H, d, OCH₃), 3.85 (1H, dd, *J* 12 and 18 Hz, *cis* C₄-H), 5.52 (1H, dd, *J* 5 and 12 Hz, C₅-H), 6.84–7.39 (8H, m, ArH), 10.29 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable); HL³, 120°, δ 2.36 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.58 (1H, dd, *J* 5 and 18 Hz, *trans* C₄-H), 3.70 (1H, dd, *J* 11 and 18 Hz, *cis* C₄-H), 5.67 (1H, dd, *J* 5 and 11 Hz, C₅-H), 6.32–8.26 (7H, m, ArH), 10.20 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable); HL⁴, 149°, δ 2.36 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.47 (1H, dd, *J* 4 and 18 Hz, *trans* C₄-H), 3.82 (1H, dd, *J* 12 and 18 Hz, *cis* C₄-H), 5.88 (1H, dd, *J* 4 and 12 Hz, C₅-H), 6.92–7.40 (7H, m, ArH), 10.20 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable). All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Synthesis of complexes : A solution of metal(II) chloride (0.01 mol) in minimum amount of ethanol was added slowly at ambient temperature to alkaline (pH 8–10) ethanolic solution of the corresponding ligand (0.02 mol) with stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h and was then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with water followed by ethanol and dried under vacuum, yields 51–65%.

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries in sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AC 300F instrument (300 MHz) using TMS as internal reference and electronic spectra (DMSO) on a Beckmann DU-64 spectrophotometer. All ligands and complexes were analyzed for C, H and N on a Carlo-Erba Strumentazion 1106 automatic elemental analyzer. The metals were determined on a Varian Techtron AA120 atomic absorption spectrometer. Molecular weight was determined by the cryoscopic method in dry DMSO. Conductance was determined with freshly prepared 1 × 10⁻³ M solutions in dry DMSO at 25° using a NDS-732 conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at 25 ± 1° using a Sherwood Scientific balance.

Acknowledgement

Instrumental facilities provided by Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Punjab University, Chandigarh, are acknowledged.

References

1. A. K. Sengupta, M. M. Gupta and A. A. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 643; M. S. Malik, V. Pal, N. K. Sangwan, K. S. Dhindsa, K. K. Verma and D. S. Bhatti, *Nematologica*, 1989, **35**, 366; N. K. Sangwan, B. S. Verma and K. S. Dhindsa, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 672; R. Malhotra, M. S. Malik, J. P. Singh and K. S. Dhindsa, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1992, **45**, 269; R. Malhotra, S. Kumar and K. S. Dhindsa, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India, Sect. A*, 1994, **64**, 21.
2. N. Singh, N. K. Sangwan and K. S. Dhindsa, *Pest Manag. Sci.*, 2000, **56**, 284.
3. A. Hooda, V. K. Garg, N. K. Sangwan and K. S. Dhindsa, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1996, **66**, 223.
4. H. A. Ead, H. M. Hassaneen, M. A. Abdallah and H. A. Mousa, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1991, **324**, 35; N. K. Sangwan, B. S. Verma and K. S. Dhindsa, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 590; K. A. Rowberg, M. Even, E. Martin and A. J. Hopfinger, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1994, **42**, 374; K. Nishimura, T. Tada, R. Shimizu and A. Ohoka, *Pestic. Sci.*, 1999, **55**, 446; R. Hasan, K. Nishimura, M. Okada, M. Akamatsu, M. Inoue, T. Veno and T. Taga, *Pestic. Sci.*, 1996, **46**, 105; J. H. H. Eusen, J. L. G. Thus, K. Wellinga and B. Stork, *Pestic. Sci.*, 1990, **29**, 101; "The Pesticide Manual", ed. C. D. S. Tomlin, 11th. ed., British Crop Protection Council, 1997.
5. N. Singh, N. K. Sangwan and K. S. Dhindsa, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1999, **29**, 673.
6. J. Elguero and A. Fruchier, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1990, 200; *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 1990, 1501.
7. N. K. Sangwan, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1987, 22.
8. C. Natarajan and P. Tharmaraj, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 666.
9. C. Natarajan and P. Tharmaraj, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 722.
10. Y. Pin and Z. Xiaoping, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1989, **37**, 61.
11. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
12. N. N. Greenwood and A. Earnshaw, "Chemistry of the Elements", Pergamon, New York, 1989.
13. D. W. Meek, R. S. Drago and T. S. Piper, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 285.
14. N. R. Rao, P. V. Rao, G. V. Reddy and M. C. Ganorkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 887.
15. M. M. Patel, H. R. Patel and K. C. Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 1.
16. D. F. Shriver, P. W. Atkin and C. K. Langfold, "Inorganic Chemistry", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1980.
17. A. K. Rana and J. R. Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 281.
18. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electron Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.